

TAYYR ERGASHEV AN EXAMPLE FOR IRRIGATORS OF KASHKADARYA

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АННОТАЦИЯ. В данной статье рассказывается о Тойыре Эргашеве, честном и преданном своему делу человеке, посвятившем свою жизнь ирригационному строительству. Будут освещены трудные путешествия этого человека и работа, проделанная в развитии управления водными ресурсами оазиса.

Основные слова. Орошение, строительство, освоение пустынь, честность, преданность делу

ABSTRACT. This article tells about Toyyr Ergashev, an honest and dedicated man who dedicated his life to irrigation construction. It will highlight the difficult journeys of this man and the work done in developing the water management of the oasis.

Basic words. Irrigation, construction, desert development, honesty, dedication

The Kashkadarya oasis, which is one of the largest geographical regions of Uzbekistan, was considered an economically backward country in the second half of the 20th century. The only way to develop here is to increase cotton raw materials. Naturally, it was considered necessary to build waterways for this. Since the 60s of the 20th century, irrigation construction in the region has risen to the level of state policy. In carrying out such work, first of all, special attention is paid to the personnel issue.

Toyir Ergashev is one of the selfless and honest people who have earned special honor and respect in the field of water management in Kashkadarya, one of the exemplary personnel who are still considered a school of will for irrigators. Toyir Ergashev was born in 1934 in the village of Dasht, Karshi district, Kashkadarya region. He was born into a working peasant family. His father, Ergash Niyazov, was a person who enjoyed special respect in the village. The life of his mother, Salvar momo Ergasheva, is also associated with fields and steppes. His childhood coincided with the war. His father, grandfather Ergash, died at the age of 54 (Farkhod took part in the construction of the hydroelectric

power station, returned after a serious illness and died about a year later). His brother Dashkul Ergashev went to war and did not return[1].

In the meantime, the eldest son, Ubaydullah, who works in one of the schools in Dehkanabad district, had to return to his village and work as a secretary in the collective farm together with his mother and brothers. With the encouragement of his brother Ubaidulla Ergashev, who shouldered the heavy burden of livelihood, Toyir Ergashev became a good specialist in water management. In 1943, Toyir Ergashev went to the 1st grade of the 7th secondary school in the village of Dasht, and in 1953 he graduated from the 10th grade of this school with a "Kumush" medal.

Irrigation of the steppe lands and cultivation of crops required a lot of work. At that time, agriculture was carried out using earthworms. Toyir Ergashev tried to become a waterman because he had felt the hardships of the peasants since childhood, working. The future irrigator, who helped his brother in the village, had a growing desire to become a mirab. Our hero remembers the words of his brother Ubaydulla: "Tairjon, none of us will be able to escape this misfortune until you go study water and become a water expert in this field. Look, not only our fields, the fields on the other side, the deserts even further away suffer from a lack of water" [2]. Tayirjon, who grew up due to the lack of water in the village, set a firm goal for himself - to bring water to the village.

In 1953-1958 he studied at the Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Mechanized Agricultural Engineering.

He began his career in 1958-1962 as a construction engineer for the Karshi Eskianhor Canal. Then he was promoted to the position of senior engineer of the regional water management organization.

In 1962-1968 he worked as the chief engineer of the Kashkadarya construction department, in 1968-1970 - deputy head of the 2nd construction and installation department of the water construction trust, in 1970-1973 he worked as deputy head of the 2nd construction and installation department of the water construction trust. head of the 2nd construction and installation department of the water construction trust.

In 1973-1981 - Chief Engineer of the Water Construction Trust, in 1981-1994 - Chief Engineer of the Karshi District Construction Department, in 1994-2001 - Head of the Regional Water Management Department, In 2001-2006 he worked in the design department of Water project as a head[3].

Toyir Ergashev's work was deservedly rewarded and received the Order of Labor Glory and the honorary title of Honored Irrigator of Uzbekistan.

He retired in 2006. He died on November 11, 2006. His family life was as fruitful as his work. Together with his wife Mekhman, he raised seven children. Ergasheva Inobat, Ergasheva Norgul, Ergashev Muzaffar work in regional organizations as engineers, hydraulic engineers. Ergasheva Dilfuza is a dentist, Ergasheva Sanobar is an accountant, Ergashev Ilgor is a master of sports.

References:

1. Nuriddinov R. Ziyo maskani. –Toshkent: “Musiq”, 2013. –B. 70.
2. Ashurov B. Pokiza iz. –Qarshi, “Nasaf”, 2004. –B. 15.
3. Аму-Қашқадарё ирригация тизимлари ҳавза бошқармаси музейи материаллари асосида
4. Shonazarov, M., & Jabbarova, I. (2024). AMIR TEMURNING HARBIY YURISHLARI VA TAKTIKALARI. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(7), 55-64.
5. Jabbarova, I., & Qodirov, I. (2024). HISTORY OF CONSTRUCTION OF RESERVOIRS WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF AGRICULTURAL POLICY OF THE SOVIET STATE IN THE KASHKADARYA OASIS. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 4(1), 47-49.
6. Nurmanov, A. Q., & Jabbarova, I. (2023). TURK XOQONLIGI HARBIY SAN’ATI. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(22), 32-40.
7. Bobomurodova, N., & Jabbarova, I. (2024, January). BERUNIYNING HINDISTON ASARI. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 103-107).
8. Jabbarova, I. (2023). HISTORY OF CONSTRUCTION OF PACHKAMAR WATER RESERVOIR. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(27), 64-70.
9. Shonazarov, M., & Jabbarova, I. (2023). O ‘ZBEK JANGCHILARINING IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHIDAGI JASORATLARI. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 160-167.

